

see table) were resistant to the chemical when compared with the most susceptible population (C), and using a resistance ratio of 5 as the demarcation.

No apparent relationship between susceptibility to this compound and the cholinesterase activity of the populations could be found, although the most resistant population (E) showed the lowest cholinesterase activity, and the least sensitivity to vamidothion. When populations E and B were compared, a resistance ratio of about 6 was found associated with an I_{50} ratio of about 5. The results indicate that reduced cholinesterase activity and a change of

Vamidothion susceptibility, cholinesterase activity, and sensitivity of rice green leafhoppers in central Taiwan.

Population	Location	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)	Resistance ratio	Cholinesterase	
				Activity (µmol/min)	I ₅₀ M
A	Shu-wang	10.57	8.7:1	0.069	4.40×10^{-4}
B	Wu-fu	5.53	4.5:1	0.093	2.70×10^{-4}
C	Hsia-tien	1.22	1.0:1	0.054	3.60×10^{-4}
D	Nay-hsin	4.07	3.3:1	0.057	5.00×10^{-4}
E	Lu-tsun	32.10	26.3:1	0.050	1.44×10^{-3}

the target site sensitivity could play a considerable role in vamidothion resistance in GLH. Electrophoretic

studies revealed qualitative differences in esterase zymograms among the populations. ■

Effect of selected insecticides on striped stem borer eggs

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Eggs of the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* in the blackhead stage were treated with candidate insecticides at 0.04% concentration. Before treatment, each egg mass was examined under the microscope to determine the initial number of eggs per mass. Three egg masses were dipped in insecticide solutions for 5 minutes then transferred to a petri dish with moistened filter paper

Effect of selected insecticides on eggs of the striped stem borer. IRRRI 1979.

Insecticide	Formulation	Eggs (initial no.)	Unhatched eggs (no.)	Ovicidal ^a activity (%)
Methyl parathion	50 EC	661	622	92.9
Carbofuran	12 F	596	593	99.4
Methomyl	90 WP	619	600	96.5
Triazophos	40 EC	656	588	89.1
Control		586	163	26.4

^a Av of 4 replications, each containing 3 egg masses.

and kept in an insectary for 48 hours. The eggs were counted again to determine the number that were unhatched. Larvae that emerged and died alter hatching

were considered hatched. Each treatment was replicated four times. The table shows the results. ■

Soil and crop management

Preference for ammonium sulfate as first topdressing in lev method of rice cultivation

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Farmers in Karchhana Tahsil, Allahabad district, commonly direct-seed rice with little field preparation after the onset of the monsoon. To control weeds, they then plow the crop with a deshia plow and plank it under flooded conditions

when plants are about 1 month old or 15–21 cm tall. The practice is locally called *lev*. Progressive farmers in the area claim that ammonium sulfate is superior to urea as the first topdressing in that rice-cultivation method. An experiment in farmers' fields was conducted to investigate the claim.

Sixteen farmers' fields, selected during 1978 kharif, were prepared with two cross plows. No basal fertilizers were applied. The variety Saket 4 was broadcast seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in the first week of July. Five weeks after

sowing the plots were plowed twice with a deshia plow and planked under flooded conditions. In the first eight plots, ammonium sulfate was topdressed immediately after plowing; in the other eight plots, urea was topdressed a week after plowing. Both fertilizer treatments were at 40 kg N/ha. The second topdressing was applied uniformly in all plots about 10 weeks after sowing with 30 kg N/ha as urea.

Visual observations 2 weeks after the first topdressing showed that weed re-establishment, weed density, and weed